

Supplemental Fig. 1

Supplemental Figure 1. Activation of HIV-1 transcription by Tat. 293T cells were transfected with vectors expressing HIV-1 LTR-*Luciferase* (lane 1) or HIV-1 LTR-*Luciferase* and HIV-1 Tat expression vectors (lane 2). After 24 hours of culturing, the cells were lysed and luciferase activity was determined using LuciLite assay.

Supplemental Fig. 2

Supplemental Figure 2. No effect of Tat-TAR NRA targeting compounds on HIV-1 reverse transcription. PBMCs were activated with PHA and IL-2 and infected with HIV-1-LUC-G. At 6 hrs p.i. DNA was extracted and analyzed by real-time PCR on Roche 4800 using primers for early LTR (panel A) and late LTR (panel) and β -globin gene as a reference. Azidothymidine (AZT) was used as control. The means \pm SD are shown ($n=3$ for each sample). Asterisk indicate $p < 0.05$.